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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
8	D8.2	D37	Digital Toolkit for monitoring and assessing R&I Impact	NUIG

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Websites, patents filing, etc.	Public	

Description (short)
<p>This deliverable presents a Digital tool which acts as a self-assessment resource for monitoring and assessing R&I Impact. The Deliverable describes the process leading to the design and development of the Toolkit including the definition of the scope and content and intended use.</p> <p>The ENLIGHT toolkit for the self-assessment of research impact awareness, literacy and readiness is a self-reflection tool designed for universities who wish to explore at an institutional level their research impact potential. The toolkit guides users through focus areas considered as relevant for universities to be research impact-driven.</p> <p>The web-based tool is available at this link Self-Assessment ENLIGHT (enlight-eu.org)</p>

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INTRODUCTION

ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT RISE

ENLIGHT is a European University Alliance to promote equitable quality of life, sustainability and global engagement through Higher Education Transformation. ENLIGHT brings together nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries (University of the Basque Country, University of Bordeaux, Comenius University Bratislava, University of Galway (formerly National University of Ireland, Galway), Ghent University, University of Göttingen, University of Groningen, University of Tartu, Uppsala University).

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Programme and more specifically within the Science With and For Society (SWAFS) Work Programme. The **ENLIGHT RISE project** (Research and Innovation agenda with and for society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT Alliance. In synergy with ENLIGHT's educational components and surrounding ecosystems, ENLIGHT RISE will deploy a comprehensive joint transformation agenda for our universities.

The ENLIGHT RISE project is structured around nine major Work Packages, of which Work Package (WP) 8 is focused on Impact. **The main objective of WP8 is to promote a mission and impact-driven research and innovation agenda.** WP8 explores the frontiers of a common impact-driven R&I agenda (task 8.1), by: analyzing the opportunities and barriers encountered to implement this agenda (8.1.3); developing actions to promote a culture of R&I impact (8.1.1); and by reviewing methods and good practices of impact assessment and measurement worldwide (8.1.2). In addition, WP8 facilitates further impact knowledge sharing with other European Universities alliances as part of the FOREU2 initiative, to spread and share solutions, successful practices, identified barriers and challenges, as well as cooperation formats and models (Task 8.2).

WP8 is led by University of the Basque Country, with Co-leads University of Galway and Ghent University. The primary focus of WP8 is the concept of "Research Impact", as distinct from R&I impact. As one of the first consensuses, WP8 leaders with the partner university representatives agreed on the following definition of research impact as ***the effects of research in the real world. Impact is the changes we can see (demonstrate, measure, capture), beyond academia (in society, economy, environment) which happen because of our research (caused by, contributed to, attributable to).***

The Digital Toolkit for monitoring and assessing R&I Impact

In line with the overall objectives of the WP, and more specifically the **Task 8.1.2 Formalize methods towards an impact-driven research & innovation agenda** and the **Sub Task Develop toolkits to monitor and self-assess impact by universities**, this report details the development and delivery of a web-based tool to monitor and self-assess impact by universities.

The ENLIGHT Toolkit for the Self-Assessment of Institutional Research Impact is a self-reflection tool designed for universities to explore, at an institutional level, their research impact awareness, literacy and readiness. The toolkit guides users through focus areas considered as relevant for universities to be research impact-driven.

The ENLIGHT SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT Toolkit is not a benchmarking tool but a diagnostic aid to identify areas of strengths and weaknesses and where there is space for improvement in the research impact environment. It is largely inspired by the work of Dr. Julie Bayley and Dr. David Phipps in particular the Institutional Health Check Workbook, (Bayley & Phipps, 2019) but also by other sources such as EARMA Impact Strategy Survey (EARMA, 2021) Vertigo Ventures Impact Landscape Survey (Vertigo Ventures, 2021) and the ACCOMPLISSH Assessment of Institutional Support and Staff Awareness of Research Impact.

The SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT Toolkit builds on the earlier work of WP8, i.e. the institutional landscaping surveys, the institutional impact literacy surveys and individual impact literacy surveys and is a key output of **Task 8.1.2 Formalize methods towards an impact-driven research & innovation agenda**. The SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT Toolkit represents a significant expansion of ENLIGHT R&I online resources accessible through the [Research & Innovation section of the ENLIGHT website](#) In particular, in the area of Impact and Impact Assessment, with the inclusion in 2022 of the earlier output of WP8 *'the repository of international good practices on research impact assessment and measurement'*. More broadly, the **SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT** Toolkit connects the institutional governance and impact-related work the ENLIGHT Work Programme effected by Erasmus+ notably the development of a methodology and a toolkit for assessing the “long-term impact of ENLIGHT on people, communities, institutions, and systems at large” with the research impact focus of WP8.

The SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT Toolkit is an **open access resource** but with additional functionality for ENLIGHT University Users. The Toolkit is interactive and multiuse, allowing users to track progress over time.

This document is organized in three main parts:

1. Chapter 1 describes the process leading to the development of the **ENLIGHT SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT Toolkit**, from its beginnings in the early Impact literacy baselining process, the further refinement of Impact literacy analysis process and finally the development of the web-based tool;
2. Chapter 2 presents the content of the **ENLIGHT SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT Toolkit** and its structure;
3. Chapter 3 presents the expected user experience.

1. THE PROCESS

The ENLIGHT **SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT** Toolkit was first developed as an Impact Literacy Assessment which in itself was developed by the WP8 Leads with reference to a number of existing works but in particular the Institutional Health Check Workbook (Bayley and Phipps, D, 2019)

The development of an Impact Literacy Survey as a means of baselining partner Universities with respect to their approach to Impact was considered at the first meetings of the WP8 Leadership Team (University of the Basque Country, University of Galway and Ghent University). Early in the initial development of the Survey, it was proposed by the WP8 Leadership Team that given the potential for a significant variation in the maturity of the processes and embedment of Impact at partner Universities, a short landscaping exercise should be carried out as a prudent first informative.

The WP8 Leadership Team agreed that the results of such a Landscaping exercise would be an essential informative step in the development of the Impact Literacy Survey. In particular to ensure that it would be appropriate and meaningful for completion by all ENLIGHT Universities irrespective of the maturity of Impact at the Institution.

1.1. Research Impact Landscaping Exercise

The proposal of an Impact Landscaping exercise was presented to the Work Package 8 team, which is made up of representatives of all 9 ENLIGHT Universities, and agreement was reached on progressing the concept during November 2021.

The WP8 Leadership Team proposed a very simple process of 3 Key Questions to be addressed for each partner University by an appropriate representative of that University.

The Questions posed by the Landscaping exercise are as follows:

Question 1 - What is your understanding of R&I Impact?

The ENLIGHT RISE definition *“Impact is the provable effects of research in the real world. Impact is the changes we can see (demonstrate, measure, capture), beyond academia (in society, economy, environment) which happen because of our research (caused by, contributed to, attributable to)”* was provided for clarity

Question 2 – Does your University have a R&I Impact policy/ implementation plan?

If so, could you please give more information about it?

Instructions Provided - *If it applies, please add a general description of the R&I Impact policy/ implementation plan accompanied by the supporting webpage links or documents.*

Question 3 - Independently of the response to the previous question, could you please identify (a) good R&I Impact practice(s) in your University?

Instructions Provided - *Please just add the name of the "good R&I Impact practices" followed by the supporting links and/or documents.*

Respondents were required to be extremely succinct in their responses, with each question response limited to just one powerpoint slide. The results of the Landscaping Exercise were presented to the full WP8 Team at a meeting in December 2021, see Figure 1 and Figure 2.

The results demonstrated that there was a significant disparity in the Institutional recognition of Research Impact among the ENLIGHT Universities.

General overview of the ENLIGHT Universities' R&I Impact landscape			
ENLIGHT University	1 Definition of Impact	2 Institutional Impact Policy	3 Good Practices
UGENT	YES. REF definition - Distinction between scientific, economic and societal impact - Impact vs. economic valorisation vs. societal value creation - Different types of impact (big, small, local, global, instrumental, conceptual)	YES. Policy Plan 2 focus areas: - framework for quality assurance and assessment via a description of the most common types of societal value creation - creating an academic environment conducive to societal value creation Comprehensive set of actions	YES. - Impact as a dimension in the evaluation approach and portfolio of research - Interdisciplinary research consortia aimed at realising societal impact - Societal Value Creation Fund - Director for Impact at Schools level - Impact Success Stories - Outreach activities
COMENIUS	NO. But agrees with proposed WP8 definition	NO.	YES. Impactful research projects vs. knowledge transfer projects
UPPSALA	NO. But agrees with proposed WP8 definition. Interested in "demonstrate, measure, capture" impact.	NO. But promotion of an Impact Implementation Logic (Impact Pathway). In-house Innovation office; Intersectoral collaboration is encouraged.	YES. Impactful research initiatives vs. Innovation projects.
UPV/EHU	NO. But agrees with proposed WP8 definition	YES. Impact is an embedded part of UPV/EHU 2030 agenda for sustainable development	YES. Analysis of the impact and contribution of UPV/EHU to the regional innovation ecosystem through a "narrative with numbers" case study (in the framework of a EC study)
NUI Galway	YES. - Similar (more elaborated) WP8 definition. - Distinction Academic vs Non-Academic Impact - Research Impact as benefit	YES. Impact is an embedded part of NUI Galway Strategic Plan 2020-2025 , which includes several impact-related flagship goals. And confirmed by NUI Galway Research and Innovation Strategy 2020-2025	YES. - Research Impact Officer - Guidance and access to resources on Research Impact (sharepoint) - Research Impact Case Studies
TARTU	YES. Tartu's Strategic Plan defines Impact in its economic dimension "increase the impact of research results on economic development through business agreements, consultation and creation, protection and rapid commercialisation of intellectual property."	YES. Impact is an embedded part of Tartu's Strategic Plan 2021-2025 . However, R&I impact indicators do not reflect societal impact , but publications, citations, external research funding, business contracts, spin-offs.	YES. - UniTartu Ventures to support research-based entrepreneurship
RUG	YES. 2013 definition - Distinction between economic and societal impact of both educational and research activities	YES. Impact is an embedded part and a pillar of RUC's Strategic Plan 2020-2026 , including a set of concrete actions to promote impact (professional support organisation, training students/ graduates, recognising/ rewarding commitment to societal impact, interdisciplinary/ inter-sectoral cooperation)	YES. - Repository of research and societal impact stories - NWO impact scout pilot (concepts to raise awareness, plan and enlarge research projects' impact).

ENLIGHT RISE Definition: "Impact is the provable effects of research in the real world. Impact is the changes we can see (demonstrate, measure, capture), beyond academia (in society; economy; environment) which happen because of our research (caused by, contributed to, attributable to)".

Figure 1 Overview of Impact Landscaping Exercise ENLIGHT WP8 Full Team Meeting December 2021 1/2

Figure 2 Overview of Impact Landscaping Exercise ENLIGHT WP8 Full Team Meeting December 2021 2/2

1.2. Impact Literacy Survey – Pilot Phase

Based on the results of the Landscaping Exercise, the WP8 Leadership Team progressed to a Pilot Phase of the Impact Literacy Survey. The Survey was developed in 2 modes 1) Researchers / Research Staff Survey 2) Institutional Mode.

The individual Researcher / Research Support Staff survey was considered important to investigate Impact Literacy in the research community as it may differ from that of the institution.

This pilot version of the Impact Literacy Survey was released in January 2022, only to the WP8 Leadership Team Universities; University of Basque Country, University of Galway and Ghent University.

Both survey modes were structured around six thematic areas of

1. Clarity
2. Context
3. Commitment
4. Capacities
5. Connectivity
6. Co-Creation

These Thematic areas were derived from the Institutional Healthcheck Workbook (Bayley, J.E. and Phipps, D, 2017) presented to the WP8 Team in November 2022 for feedback.

Research Impact Literacy Survey: FIRST DRAFT

Proposal for Structure

Assessing the current situation, but also trends/on-going processes

- 1. CLARITY**
 - Knowledge, understanding and valorisation of research impact
- 2. CONTEXT: looking at the external research impact drivers**
 - Regional/ national policy, frameworks, research quality assessment processes, funding criteria
- 3. COMMITMENT**
 - Institutional Impact Strategies/ Plans/ Policies (stand-alone vs. embedded) and links to regional, European and global (UN SDGs) policy priorities
 - Institutional leadership of R&I impact
- 4. CAPACITIES**
 - Dedicated support and advice services
 - Funding and staff resources for impact delivery
 - Recognition and investment in the development of impact-related skills (staff training & education)
- 5. CONNECTIVITY**
 - How the organisational units work together and connect to the overall strategy
- 6. CO-CREATION**
 - Engagement with non-academics to generate impactful research

Figure 3 Thematic Areas of Impact Literacy Surveys ENLIGHT WP8 Full Team Meeting November 2021

The Pilot Surveys included compulsory and subsidiary Questions as shown in Figure 4

Research Impact Literacy Surveys

Preparation of the analysis phase

DIMENSION	Institutional Survey		Researchers & Research Support Staff Survey	
	Nº of major compulsory questions (points)	Subsidiary questions	Nº of major compulsory questions (points)	Subsidiary questions
1- CLARITY	3	3 (for further elaboration)	3	3 (for further elaboration)
2- CONTEXT	2	2 (for further elaboration)	2	2 (for further elaboration)
3- COMMITMENT	3	6 (additional related questions or for further elaboration)	2	2 (for further elaboration)
4 - CAPACITIES	10	3 (for further elaboration)	9	3 (for further elaboration)
5 - CONNECTIVITY	3	1 for further elaboration on the 3 major questions	3	1 for further elaboration on the 3 major questions
6 - CO-CREATION	3	2 (additional related questions or for further elaboration)	1	4 (additional related questions or for further elaboration)
TOTAL	24	17	20	15

Figure 4 Pilot Impact Literacy Survey Summary ENLIGHT WP8 Leadership Team Meeting January 2022

1.3. Impact Literacy Survey – Final

Based on the experience of the Pilot Survey, the WP8 Leadership Team moved towards the development of the Final Impact Literacy Survey. The most substantive changes to that of the Pilot Phase were

- **Use of UGent Qualtrics** to run the survey
- Integration of an **Information and Consent Form** following UGent's ethics and data protection policies and procedures, and adapting it to the specifics of ENLIGHT RISE.
- **Removal of potential personal identifiers** (e.g.: job function, faculty/ school/ department). Email question for further clarifications remains optional at the end of the survey.
- Further **simplification of the survey:**
 - Definition of the different survey sections (e.g. clarity, context, commitment, connectivity, competencies& resources, co-creation)
 - Review of the questions
 - Further development questions only appear when the answer is “yes or possibly/partly”

In March 2022, the Final Survey was presented to the full WP8 team with notification that two survey modes would be available, see Figure 5.

In April 2022, links to the two survey modes were circulated to all partner Universities via the WP8 representatives. The period of response was indicated to remain available initially until end of April 2022 with a later extension to May 2022.

Research Impact Literacy Survey(s)

Sending of the Research Impact Literacy Survey(s) to all Universities

2 SURVEYS with 2 different Target Groups

INSTITUTIONAL Impact Literacy Survey	RESEARCHERS AND RESEARCH SUPPORT STAFF Impact Literacy Survey
1 response per University	Multiple responses are possible (and welcome)
From the Senior Management Team (e.g. Vice-rectorate/Support Service/ Specialised Committee)	Researchers (PhD students, early career, senior researchers, etc.) Research Support Staff (e.g. Research administrators, advisors, research project managers, etc.)

Figure 5 Impact Literacy Survey Update ENLIGHT WP8 Full Team Meeting March 2022

1.4. Main Conclusions of the Impact Literacy Survey

Following the extended response period and analysis by UPV, the results of the Final Impact Literacy Surveys were presented to the WP8 Team in July 2022. The results are summarized in the following Figures from the July Meeting.

Figure 6 Summary of Impact Literacy Survey Results ENLIGHT WP8 Full Team Meeting July 2022 1/2

Figure 7 Summary of Impact Literacy Survey Results ENLIGHT WP8 Full Team Meeting July 2022 2/2

1.5. Web-based tool development

In September 2022, leveraging the work carried out on the refinement of the Impact Literacy Survey, it was proposed by the ENLIGHT WP8 Leadership Team that the Final Impact Literacy

Survey would form the basis of a Digital Toolkit for the monitoring and self-assessment of Impact by Partner Universities.

This proposal was put to the full ENLIGHT WP8 Team in September 2022, see Figure 8, extract from meeting. Following acceptance of this proposal the development of the toolkit was progressed led by UPV with the engagement of a website developer. At a further consultation with the full ENLIGHT WP8 Team in October 2022, it was agreed that the Toolkit would focus in line with the relevant Task description, only on the institutional survey. With timelines very short for development, once consensus was reached, UPV/University of the Basque Country proceeded to liaise with the website developer on a brief.

The approach to the Toolkit was modelled on the existing [HEinnovate self-assessment tool](https://heinnovate.eu/en) developed by the European Commission /OECD on Universities' entrepreneurship <https://heinnovate.eu/en>.

Consultation with the WP8 Leadership Team on the proposed Structure, Draft Texts and Survey Questions was carried out in mid-December 2022.

Consultation with the full ENLIGHT WP8 Team on the first iteration of the Digital Toolkit was carried out at a WP8 ENLIGHT Full Team meeting at the end of January 2023. At this meeting, the issues surrounding licensing/copyright for publication of the Digital Toolkit were raised, and the Team was informed of the consultations initiated with Emerald Publishing Group to clarify the potential public use of the Toolkit beyond ENLIGHT universities. As of the date of submission of this Deliverable, this consultation process has not concluded yet.

TASKS: Discussion

Task 8.1.2.
Develop TOOLKITS to MONITOR and SELF-ASSESS impact by universities.
 Deliverable and Milestone: Digital toolkit to monitor and for self-assessment of R&I agendas (M18: 28 Feb 2023)

PROPOSAL:

- For the 1st version of the toolkit focus on the self-assessment dimension
- Use an improved/revise version of the Impact Literacy Survey(s) carried out in early 2022
- Possibility of hosting it at the repository webpage. This would mean:
 - micro-site as part of the repository
 - using the same visual style
 - possibility of exporting data and (optional) of visualising results
 - possibility of making automatic data/statistical analysis
 - it does not allow the registration of previous responses after a second consultation
 - access would be given to everyone. Alternatively, a simple access code could be shared within ENLIGHT.

Figure 8 Proposal of Development of Monitoring and Self-Assessment Toolkit - ENLIGHT WP8 Full Team Meeting September 2022

Digital toolkit for self-assessment of impact

Web developer first proposal
<https://impact.enlight-eu.org/self-assessment>

Work in progress. Web developer is integrating:

- **Comments on design** (e.g. "home page"; the "dimensions"; ...)
- **Comments on content** (e.g. repeating question; small editing changes not included)
- **Visualisation of results to be further improved**, including administrator visualisation of results
- **Emerald issue**

Figure 9 Presentation of First Iteration of ENLIGHT SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT Toolkit - - ENLIGHT WP8 Full Team Meeting September 2022

2. THE DIGITAL TOOLKIT

In this section we present the contents of the **ENLIGHT SELF-ASSESSMENT OF INSTITUTIONAL RESEARCH IMPACT Toolkit** (The Toolkit) as published at the time of submission of this Deliverable mid-February 2023.

2.1. Landing Page

Figure 10 <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/self-assessment> Landing Page Graphic

The landing page is accessed via the ENLIGHT website or directly at <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/self-assessment>

The Landing page includes

1. A brief Introduction of the Toolkit
2. A description of the ENLIGHT University Alliance and the context of the Toolkit in ENLIGHT RISE
3. Access to the Self-Assessment Toolkit
4. Consent for Participation

2.1.1 Introductory Text

The Introductory text is self-explanatory and briefly presents the Toolkit while linking to the ENLIGHT Repository of Good Practice at <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/understanding-research-impact>

(THE Introductory Text)

The ENLIGHT toolkit for the self-assessment of research impact awareness, literacy and readiness is a self-reflection tool designed for universities who wish to explore at an institutional level their research impact potential. The toolkit guides users through focus areas considered as relevant for universities to be research impact-driven.

The toolkit is not a benchmarking tool but a diagnostic aid to identify areas of strengths and weaknesses and where there is space for improvement in the research impact environment. It is largely inspired by the [Institutional Health check Workbook](#) of Dr David Phipps and Dr Julie Bayley, but also by other sources such as [EARMA Impact Strategy Survey](#), [Vertigo Ventures Impact Landscape Survey](#) and the [ACCOMPLISSH Assessment of Institutional Support and Staff Awareness of Research Impact](#).

The toolkit can be used in 2 user modes: 1) as a university management staff member; 2) as an academic/researcher or member of research support staff. The toolkit consists of 19 major questions organised around 6 major focus areas and provides the user with instant access to results. The toolkit is free, confidential and open to anyone to use. [Read more](#).

2.1.2 ABOUT US

The **ABOUT US** Section of the landing page includes a brief description of the ENLIGHT University Alliance and the context of the Toolkit in ENLIGHT RISE and invites users to learn more by connecting or exploring other WP outputs.

ABOUT US

IMPACT is at the core of the mission of the [European University Alliance ENLIGHT](#) and, as such, one of its main objectives is to promote an impact-based culture both within and beyond ENLIGHT universities. This includes the promotion of a model of good practice of impact-directed management and the integration of impact across Higher Education, Research and Innovation activities.

The University Research Impact Awareness, Literacy and Readiness self-assessment toolkit is one of a number of project outputs of the ENLIGHT research impact team to achieve these objectives. It is specifically designed for universities, both within and beyond the ENLIGHT network, who wish to explore their research impact potential.

In the context of the ENLIGHT project, we understand impact as the effects or changes that we can see (demonstrate, measure, capture) beyond academia (on society, economy, environment, etc.) which happen because of an activity in the higher education environment. [Read more.](#)

Do you need more information about our ENLIGHT impact-related work?

Please [contact us here.](#)

2.1.3 SELF-ASSESSMENT

This section links to the Self-Assessment with direction to the details of **CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION**

SELF-ASSESSMENT

Before you start the self-assessment please read carefully the information document [here.](#) You will be asked to provide your consent to the [ENLIGHT research impact team](#) to process, store, analyse and report on the data that is gathered. In doing so, all necessary measures will be taken to protect the confidentiality of your personal data.

Please be also aware that your responses will not be registered if you leave the tool before answering all its questions. So please foresee some time (10 minutes approximately) to go through the 19 multiple-option questions.

START

2.1.4 CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION

This section is presented in 3 main subsections

- *Consent for participation*
- *Consent for the processing of personal data*
- *Consent about the reuse and sharing of data*

CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION

- ***I voluntarily participate in this self-assessment exercise and give permission to the ENLIGHT research impact team to process, store, analyze and report on my data.***
- ***I know that I may withdraw from the exercise at any time without giving a reason for this decision and without it affecting in any way my continued relationship with the persons behind the self-assessment.***
- ***I have read the information document [here](#) and have received sufficient explanation of the nature, purpose, duration and anticipated effects of the exercise. I was given the opportunity to ask questions and I received satisfactory answers to all my questions.***

Consent for the processing of personal data

- ***I have read the information document [here](#) and I know that I have rights to safeguard my privacy (including access, correction, deletion) and to whom I should turn to exercise these rights.***
- ***I give permission to the identified contact persons to collect, process and store (personal) data from me for the purposes of the self-assessment exercise.***

Consent about the reuse and sharing of data

- I give permission to share my data for further analysis and study. In doing so, all**

Yes No

2.2 IDENTIFICATION

This section allows the user to select their University, if an ENLIGHT Partner, or 'Other' if not.

IDENTIFICATION

Your university

- University of Bordeaux Ghent University Comenius University Bratislava University of the Basque Country
- University of Galway University of Göttingen University of Groningen University of Tartu
- Uppsala University Other

I am answering as...

- Member of the university management staff Academic / research staff Research support staff

< PREVIOUS

NEXT >

2.3 CLARITY

CLARITY

This dimension reflects how clearly university management, academics, researchers and research support staff understand research impact as well as their role in contributing to it.

Having a well-developed research impact strategy and dedicated resources is not sufficient for being impact ready. It is important that staff share a common understanding of what research impact is and what it is not; are aware of the existence (or inexistence) of institutional strategies for research impact and have a clear view of what is their role in it.

Do you want to know more about the research impact concept? Please click [here](#).

1. Does your university have a research impact definition (it could be in the form of a statement, a policy objective, etc.)?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

2. Do you know what research impact is?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

3. Do you understand your "role" in contributing to research impact?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

2.4 CONTEXT

CONTEXT

This dimension takes into consideration how external factors may influence universities, academic, research and research support staff impact readiness.

The increased attention and support for research impact is driven by a number of 'external' factors including national policy, funders' requirements and research assessment related elements. Despite this common trend, the approaches are often different. In some cases, researchers are expected to outline their plan for impact and receive funding on the promise of impact success; in other cases, large retrospective assessment exercises are set up making researchers eligible for future funding.

Do you want to know more about the different policy frameworks and approaches for promoting research impact? Please click [here](#).

4. Does research impact play a role within your national/ regional research quality assessment, policy or frameworks?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

5. Is research impact incorporated into the research proposal templates of your national /regional funding agencies?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

PLEASE FEEL FREE TO PROVIDE MORE DETAILS.

2.5 COMMITMENT

COMMITMENT

This dimension reflects the extent to which the university is committed to research impact through strategy and recognition.

A research impact-driven university supposes there is commitment across the institution and at all levels of action. Commitment may take many forms. The most comprehensive approach would be the adoption of a research impact policy that underpins a strategic plan and is effected by an implementation plan that is adequately and appropriately resourced. However, this comprehensive approach is not a prerequisite to achieving, recording and assessing impactful research, but the support of institutional structures, policies and processes certainly is.

Do you want to know more about different universities' strategic approaches for promoting research impact? Please click [here](#).

6. Is research impact a strategic priority for your university?

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

7. Is there institutional leadership in research impact?

There is institutional leadership in research impact at your university.

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

8. How do you expect your university will prioritise around research impact in the coming 5 years?

- Greatly increase prioritisation
 Possible increase prioritisation
 Reduce prioritization
 Don't know

9. Do incentive and reward structures recognize research impact related work?

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

PLEASE FEEL FREE TO PROVIDE MORE DETAILS.

2.6 CAPABILITES & RESOURCES

CAPACITIES & RESOURCES

This dimension reflects in a non-exhaustive way relevant capacities and resources that need to be in place to sustain and maximise universities' research impact readiness.

The organizational capacities and resources of a university drive its ability and readiness to deliver on its research impact strategy and commitment. Impact-related support and advice, systems, tools, funding, people, competencies, expertise and knowledge are all important conditions within a university for promoting and managing research impact.

10. Is there dedicated support and advice available for research impact?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

11. Are there dedicated systems (repositories, tools, platforms, etc.) to support research impact information?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

12. Do you follow a specific methodology (or methodologies) for measuring/ assessing research impact?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

13. Does your university offer/ support training in research impact-related skills?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

14. Have you ever participated in a training to develop research impact skills?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

2.7 CONNECTIVITY

CONNECTIVITY

This dimension reflects the extent to which the different university teams (e.g. research groups, support units, etc.) work together, how they connect to an overall strategy ad how cohesive these relationships are.

15. Do teams within the university who support research impact work together (e.g. research groups, support units, etc.)?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

16. Are the different teams' research impact activities aligned with the university's strategy?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

17. Are the varied research impact activities (e.g. monitoring, assessment, promotion, etc.) done in a coordinated way at your university?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

2.8 CO-CREATION

CO-CREATION

This dimension reflects the extent and type of engagement with societal stakeholders to generate impactful research.

Communication and dissemination of science results is important but not enough to bring about impact. Impact can only happen if research is used and brings about a change beyond academia, thus it is essential to engage with societal stakeholders throughout all the research life-cycle phases: from the early moments of project design, to the uptake, adoption and use of project outcomes.

By societal stakeholders we understand business organisations, policy makers and public administration, civil society organisations, citizens, etc.

18. Do you work with societal stakeholders in the framework of your research impact activities?

Yes

Possibly/Partly

No

Don't know

PLEASE ADD ANY OTHER RELEVANT INFORMATION YOU WOULD LIKE TO SHARE WITH THE ENLIGHT IMPACT TEAM.

[← PREVIOUS](#)

[SUBMIT](#)

3. THE USER EXPERIENCE

In this section we present the USER Experience as a non-ENLIGHT University Research Support Staff respondent <https://impact.enlight-eu.org/self-assessment>.

3.1 CAPABILITES & RESOURCES

IDENTIFICATION

Your university

- University of Bordeaux
- Ghent University
- Comenius University Bratislava
- University of the Basque Country
- University of Galway
- University of Göttingen
- University of Groningen
- University of Tartu
- Uppsala University
- Other

TEST FOR DELIVERABLE

I am answering as...

- Member of the university management staff
- Academic / research staff
- Research support staff

< PREVIOUS

NEXT >

3.1 CLARITY

CLARITY

This dimension reflects how clearly university management, academics, researchers and research support staff understand research impact as well as their role in contributing to it.

Having a well-developed research impact strategy and dedicated resources is not sufficient for being impact ready. It is important that staff share a common understanding of what research impact is and what it is not; are aware of the existence (or inexistence) of institutional strategies for research impact and have a clear view of what is their role in it.

Do you want to know more about the research impact concept? Please click [here](#).

1. Does your university have a research impact definition (it could be in the form of a statement, a policy objective, etc.)?

- Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

2. Do you know what research impact is?

- Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

PLEASE PROVIDE YOUR DEFINITION.

3. Do you understand your "role" in contributing to research impact?

- Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

3.2 CONTEXT

CONTEXT

This dimension takes into consideration how external factors may influence universities, academic, research and research support staff impact readiness.

The increased attention and support for research impact is driven by a number of 'external' factors including national policy, funders' requirements and research assessment related elements. Despite this common trend, the approaches are often different. In some cases, researchers are expected to outline their plan for impact and receive funding on the promise of impact success; in other cases, large retrospective assessment exercises are set up making researchers eligible for future funding.

Do you want to know more about the different policy frameworks and approaches for promoting research impact? Please click [here](#).

4. Does research impact play a role within your national/ regional research quality assessment, policy or frameworks?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

5. Is research impact incorporated into the research proposal templates of your national /regional funding agencies?

Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

PLEASE FEEL FREE TO PROVIDE MORE DETAILS.

3.3 COMMITMENT

COMMITMENT

This dimension reflects the extent to which the university is committed to research impact through strategy and recognition.

A research impact-driven university supposes there is commitment across the institution and at all levels of action. Commitment may take many forms. The most comprehensive approach would be the adoption of a research impact policy that underpins a strategic plan and is effected by an implementation plan that is adequately and appropriately resourced. However, this comprehensive approach is not a prerequisite to achieving, recording and assessing impactful research, but the support of institutional structures, policies and processes certainly is.

Do you want to know more about different universities' strategic approaches for promoting research impact? Please [click here](#).

6. Is research impact a strategic priority for your university?

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

7. Is there institutional leadership in research impact?

There is institutional leadership in research impact at your university.

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

8. How do you expect your university will prioritise around research impact in the coming 5 years?

- Greatly increase prioritisation
 Possible increase prioritisation
 Reduce prioritization
 Don't know

9. Do incentive and reward structures recognize research impact related work?

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

3.4 CAPACITIES & RESOURCES

CAPACITIES & RESOURCES

This dimension reflects in a non-exhaustive way relevant capacities and resources that need to be in place to sustain and maximise universities' research impact readiness.

The organizational capacities and resources of a university drive its ability and readiness to deliver on its research impact strategy and commitment. Impact-related support and advice, systems, tools, funding, people, competencies, expertise and knowledge are all important conditions within a university for promoting and managing research impact.

10. Is there dedicated support and advice available for research impact?

- Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

WHO IS RESPONSIBLE FOR MONITORING, ASSESSING AND/OR PROMOTING RESEARCH IMPACT AT YOUR UNIVERSITY?

11. Are there dedicated systems (repositories, tools, platforms, etc.) to support research impact information?

- Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

PLEASE FEEL FREE TO PROVIDE DETAILS.

12. Do you follow a specific methodology (or methodologies) for measuring/ assessing research impact?

- Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

13. Does your university offer/ support training in research impact-related skills?

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

14. Have you ever participated in a training to develop research impact skills?

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

3.5 CONNECTIVITY

CONNECTIVITY

This dimension reflects the extent to which the different university teams (e.g. research groups, support units, etc.) work together, how they connect to an overall strategy and how cohesive these relationships are.

15. Do teams within the university who support research impact work together (e.g. research groups, support units, etc.)?

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

16. Are the different teams' research impact activities aligned with the university's strategy?

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

17. Are the varied research impact activities (e.g. monitoring, assessment, promotion, etc.) done in a coordinated way at your university?

- Yes
 Possibly/Partly
 No
 Don't know

3.6 CO-CREATION

18. Do you work with societal stakeholders in the framework of your research impact activities?

- Yes Possibly/Partly No Don't know

19. In case of positive response, what is the most common level of collaboration?

- Collaboration for data collection and/ or contrast of the project results Collaboration as potential end users of the project results or in order to share and / or co-participate in the project's dissemination tasks Co-design of the project, the societal stakeholders have participated in the definition of the project and its objectives Co-creation throughout all phases of the project: design, implementation, preparation of results

PLEASE ADD ANY OTHER RELEVANT INFORMATION YOU WOULD LIKE TO SHARE WITH THE ENLIGHT IMPACT TEAM.

[< PREVIOUS](#)

[SUBMIT](#)

3.7 RESULTS

Based on the responses submitted shown in Sections 3.1 to 3.6 above, the results below were generated on screen showing in this case a high degree of research impact maturity of the respondent's institution.

New submission added to Self-assessment of Universities Research Impact Awareness, Literacy and Readiness.

[BACK TO FORM](#)

Self-assessment of Universities Research Impact Awareness, Literacy and Readiness - Results

Submitted:
2023-02-14

Institution:
TEST FOR DELIVERABLE

Role:
Research support staff

[PRINT OR CREATE PDF](#)

The Toolkit is a self-reflection, self-assessment resource and bespoke recommendations of steps to be taken for self-improvement are not provided. However, the results page which is also available as a downloadable pdf, sample included at **Annex A** of this report, cross-references and links to the relevant sections of the ENLIGHT repository of good practice providing valuable guidance.

References

Bayley, J. and Phipps, D. Extending the concept of research impact literacy: levels of literacy, institutional role and ethical considerations [version 2; peer review: 2 approved]. *Emerald Open Res* 2019, 1:14
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Bayley, J. and Phipps, D. Institutional Healthcheck Workbook. *Emerald Publishing Limited* 2019 (<https://www.emeraldpublishing.com/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/Emerald-Resources-Institutional-Healthcheck-Workbook.pdf>)

European Commission - ACCOMPLISH, D4.2 Assessment of Institutional Support and Staff Awareness of Research Impact Across ACCOMPLISH Partner Institutions. *European Commission* 2017
(<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b56fb43a&appId=PPGMS>)

European Commission - ENLIGHT RISE, D8.1 Web-based repository and tool for mutual learning on R&I Impact. *European Commission* 2022 (DRAFT AWAITING EUROPEAN COMMISSION APPROVAL)

Uhrig, B. and Jackson, A. EARMA Policy and Representation Committee November 2019-April 2020, Impact Strategy Survey Summary and Results. *EARMA* 2021
(<https://earma.org/publications/>)

Vertigo Ventures, Impact Landscape Survey 2021. *Vertigo Ventures* 2021
(<https://hive.tech/impact-landscape-survey-2021-2/>)

ANNEX A

2/14/23, 5:41 PM

Self-assessment of Universities Research Impact Awareness, Literacy and Readiness | ENLIGHT

Self-assessment of Universities Research Impact Awareness, Literacy and Readiness - Results

Submitted:
2023-03-14

Institution:
TEST FOR DELIVERABLE

Role:
Research support staff

Comparison with other results from your university

Comparing your results against the results obtained for your university and your role

<https://impact.enlight-eu.org/form/self-assessment/confirmation?token=FN7S5yIk42B-WpSyvduB6qQAh1UXLqXORSxur2kXomU#>

1/2

ENLIGHT		Detailed Results	
	Clarity		15 / 15
	- Your university has a research impact definition.		5
	- You know what research impact is.		5
	- You understand your role in contributing to research impact.		5
→	For further information and guidance, please consult the "understanding research impact" section at our ENLIGHT repository of good practices.		
	Context		10 / 10
	- Research impact plays a role within your national/ regional research quality assessment, policy or frameworks.		5
	- Research impact is incorporated into the research proposal templates of your national/ regional funding agencies.		5
→	For further information, please consult the "policy frameworks" section at our ENLIGHT repository of good practices.		
	Commitment		20 / 20
	- Research impact is a strategic priority for your university.		5
	- There is institutional leadership in research impact at your university.		5
	- You expect your university to prioritise around research impact in the coming 5 years.		5
	- Incentive and reward structures recognise research impact related work at your university.		5
→	For further information and guidance, please consult the "HEIs policies" section at our ENLIGHT repository of good practices.		
	Capacities & Resources		25 / 25
	- There is dedicated support and advice available for research impact at your university.		5
	- There are dedicated systems (repositories, tools, platforms, etc.) to support research impact information at your university.		5
	- You follow a specific methodology (or methodologies) for measuring/ assessing research impact.		5
	- Your university offers/ supports training in research impact-related skills.		5
	- You have participated in training to develop research impact skills.		5
→	For further information and guidance, please consult the "Methodologies" section at our ENLIGHT repository of good practices.		